

Description

The Robotics Assisted Farming Model enables the usage of aeroponics as well as hydroponics with the assistance of automation and artificial intelligence. The whole process is made successful with the usage of ATMEGA2560 & Broadcom BCM2711 & (SoC) ESP8266 Microcontrollers and many more sensors.

Target Areas :

Agricultural Farms, Farming Research Labs and Home.

Features

- Hydroponics System
- Aeroponics System
- Auto Seeding
- Mobile Based GUI
- Plant Disease Detection
- Auto Nutritional Maintenance System
- Inbuilt Lighting System
- Auto Cooling System
- Database to store the data.

Hydroponics System

The system enables the usage of hydroponics by using centrifugal pumps and a very reliable water drainage system.

Aeroponic System

The system is equipped with a good water mist creating mechanism which enables the system to use aeroponics.

Auto Seeding

The system has a x and y axis moving mechanism with BO motors with accuracy more than 85% by which we can seed the whole system easily.

Mobile Based UI

The system has a user-friendly mobile application that is useful while using this device. The app enables the user to get the real - time information of the system like the parameters as well as the live footage of the farm. It also tells the user about the suggestive measures needed to be taken.

Plant Detection

The system has a plant detection algorithm in which the software will identify the amount of diseases the plant has with the help of Convolutional Neural Network and Normalized Difference Vegetation index in Python with OPENCV and TensorFlow.

Auto Nutritional Maintenance

The system is equipped with ph, tds, humidity and temperature sensor which helps the system to identify the amount of nutrition the system has and provides it at an equilibrium state with the help of different peristaltic pumps.

SPECIFICATIONS-

MCU AND MPUs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Atmega 2560 2. Esp8266 (SOC) 3. BSM2711
Sensors	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. DS18B20 2. DHT11 3. LIQUID pH SENSOR 4. TDS SENSOR
CONNECTIVITY	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. WIFI 802.11N IEEE
PERIPHERALS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CAMERA 2. PERISTALTIC PUMPS 3. BO MOTORS 4. CENTRIFUGAL PUMPS 5. SERVO

Height	28.5 inch
Width	15 inch
Length	20 inch

Button 1	Reset
Button 2	Aeroponics Mode
Button 3	Hydroponics Mode
Button 4	Sowing Mode
Button 5	Plant 1 (Low Nutri)
Button 6	Plant 2 (High Nutri)